

ABOUT THE MEANINGFUL STRUCTURE OF THE SENTENCE

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Abstract:

In the same way that the units that appear as linguistic units but have communicative-significant properties other than nominative-denotative properties are recorded as predicative units, specific opinions are expressed about their propositional structure. According to this basis, the sentence was noted as the most minimal of the speech derivative constructions, and important views related to the definition of its structural, semantic, and pragmatic features were put forward.

Key words: sentence, proposition, presupposition, word, language, speech, language and speech units, theme-rhema, structural, semantic, and pragmatic factors.

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Derivation of word combinations

As we approach the issue of word formation on the basis of derivational law, in this work we use the terms of derivation known as operand, operator, derivative. Here, the operand represents the element before the derivation process. The operator is the main element of derivation, which requires a linguistic unit or tool to be imported into the derivation process. A derivative is a product of a derivative.

In the first chapter of our work, we thought about syntactic devices, more precisely, some issues specific to the sentence and its manifestations (propositional and predicative signs of the sentence). However, it is important to pay particular attention to the fact that in the formation of such syntactic devices, their constituents, that is, participating components, may not always be purely nominative. We have our own reasons for expressing this opinion. Any word has its own nominative aspect as well as its own communicative aspect. In this case, it is not justified to say that its semantics arises directly, without any influence. In this situation, the emergence of each unit occurs only due to pragmatic needs. Therefore, if we recognize the presence of semantic and pragmatic features in a word, its syntax (more precisely, syntagmatics) is an undeniable reality.

According to the majority of existing linguistic literature, the concept of artificial word is a unit formed by some existing method of word formation in linguistics. One of the main signs in it is the emergence of a new meaning, in other words, a new expression. In our opinion, this is an undeniable fact.

Many opinions have been expressed in linguistic sources about morphological (affixation), syntactic (composition), semantic, syntactic-lexical methods of word formation. These thoughts and views have served our science and education until today.

When expressing his opinion on word formation, A. Hojiyev said that the word formation combination has two meanings, that it generally refers to the formation of a new

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word and the formation of a word with the help of language units in a certain way, with this second meaning "word specially emphasizes that the compound "making" is considered a linguistic term, it means a linguistic concept, and the form of this compound "making a word" (relative form with -l affix) is also widely used. According to A. Hajiyev's book "Word formation system of the Uzbek language", it is necessary to pay attention to which ratio form it is. Because this thing plays a role in determining the essence of events related to word formation (word formation, word formation). It is known that the singular and passive forms of the verb can be formed with the help of this suffix. The verb form in the linguistic term "formation of words" is the passive participle. This term ("word formation") cannot be used in the relative form and sense of the self. Because "making words" means "making words with the help of special language combinations, in a certain way", this phenomenon cannot be unrelated to the subject (performer). "Word formation of the Uzbek language" refers to the field of Uzbek linguistics, as does the term "word formation", phonetics, and morphology. So, the term "word formation" has two meanings: 1) the meaning of "field" mentioned now; 2) passive form and meaning of the term "word formation" defined above. "Word formation" as a separate field (department) of linguistics is a teaching about word formation and related units and phenomena, generally speaking, about the system of word formation. As the term "word formation" refers to the formation of words using language units in a certain way, it is necessary to focus on this issue - the method of word formation. A lot of work has been done; a lot has been said about the method (methods) of word formation. However, the essence of this phenomenon has not been clearly defined in Uzbek linguistics, and no consensus has been reached on this issue. As a result, in addition to the fact that the nature of many phenomena related to word formation is not properly covered, the "word formation" debate is bringing things that have nothing to do with this system. This also has a negative effect on the correct solution of the issues related to the artificial word. For example, when Sh. Shoabdurahmanov, M. Askarova, A. Hojiyev, I. Rasulov, Kh. Doniyorov commented on word formation in the textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language", word formation is one of the independent fields of linguistics (like lexicology, grammar), and it is a new word formation, word formation methods and, in general, the study of events related to word formation, the term word formation is applied to two types of phenomena: 1) in general, word formation, the phenomenon of word formation; 2) it is noted that it refers to the branch of linguistics that studies phenomena related to word formation. According to this book, creating a word is creating a new word, regardless of the method, according to which it is indicated: work + chi - worker, now + answer - now answer, five year + year - five years.

According to this textbook, it is noted that in the process of language development, as well as in its lexicon, grammatical structure and other areas, various changes may occur in the field of word formation. As an example of this, attention is paid to the fact that the active or passive types of word formation may be different in different periods, or that a word that was historically fictional may not be considered fictional from the point of view of current formation. In this textbook, another aspect related to the essence of the issue is noteworthy. According to him, there are a lot of made-up words in the modern Uzbek language, but their formation can be related to historical or current formation, and special importance is attached to the need to distinguish between these two phenomena in the analysis of word formation.

In the textbook, there are also reasonable ideas about the study of word formation by dividing it into modern word formation and historical word formation. According to it, it is stated that the relationship between the components of the artificial word in the formation of the current (synchronous) word is alive, its meaning can be justified by the semantic

relationship of its components, in other words, such a relationship is clearly felt, and for proof of opinion (ter + im, + im, or+im; arra+la, randa+la, ego+la; insof+siz, sazaad+siz, korim+siz) are examples. The book explains in detail that when it comes to historical construction, historical (diachronic) construction cannot be justified as above, and the construction and meaning of this word can be determined through special investigations and historical observations. An example is a blanket: the word blanket means something made of cotton or something else, which is covered when lying down, and the affix -cha means to shrink, but the word blanket does not mean "small blanket", but a blanket with cotton or something else inside it. It is scientifically proven that the meaning of the word "blanket" cannot be based on the meaning of its "blanket" and other parts. At the same time, it is shown that the current word "blanket" should not be separated into "blanket" and "cha" components, but how it became a word expressing such a meaning, it should be checked, and it should be studied to make a historical (diachronic) word.

References:

[1]. Qurbonova M., Sayfullaeva R., Boqieva G., Mengliev B. *Structural syntax of the Uzbek language. Study guide.* - Tashkent. 2004. (-B. 52) -142 p. (Kurbonova M., Sayfullaeva R., Bokieva G., Mengliev B. *Structural syntax of the Uzbek language. Ukuv kullanmasi.* - Tashkent. 2004. (-B. 52) -142 p.)

[2]. Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A. *Theoretical grammar of the Uzbek language (Syntax).* - Tashkent: "Teacher" 1995, (- P.5-6) 195 p. 9 Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A. *Theoretical grammar of the Uzbek language (Syntax).* - Tashkent: "Ukitchich" 1995, (- B.5-6) 195 p.)

[3]. Moskalskaya O.I. *Problemy system description syntax.* -M., 1974, -S. 9-19; 2-e izdanie. -M., 1981, -S. 9-18; (Moskalskaya O.I. *Problemi sistemnogo opisania sintaktisa.* -M., 1974, -S. 9-19; 2nd izdanie. -M., 1981, -S. 9-18)

[4]. Nurmonov A., Mahmudov N., Akhmedov A., Solikhajhaeva S. *Meaningful syntax of the Uzbek language.* Uz FA "Fan" publishing house, 1992, -B.28 (Nurmonov A., Mahmudov N., Akhmedov A., Solikhujhaeva S. *Meaningful syntax of the Uzbek language.* Uz FA "Fan" publishing house, 1992, -B.28)

[5]. Paducheva, Ye. V. *Semanticheskie issledovaniya: semantika vremeni i vida v russskom yazyke; narrative semantics / Ye. V. Paducheva.* - Moscow: Shkola "Yazyki russkoy kultury", 1996. -465 p. (Paducheva, E. V. *Semanticheskie issledovaniya: semantika vremeni i vida v russskom yazike; semantic narrative / E. V. Paducheva.* - Moscow: Shkola "Yaziki russkoy kulturi", 1996. -465 p.)

[6]. Prokopovich N.N. *Voprosy syntaxisa russkogo yazyka.* -M.: Vysshaya shkola, 1974, 350 p. (Prokopovich N.N. *Voprosi syntaxisa russkogo yazika.* -M.: Visshaya shkola, 1974, 350 p.)